

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The Labor Force Participation Rate at World Level

Between 2013 and 2021, the value of labor force participation grew by an average of 0.58%

The World Bank calculates the value of the labor force participation rate. The labor force participation rate is the percentage of the population aged 15-64 who are economically active: all people who provide work to produce goods and services during a given period.

Ranking of countries by global labor force participation rate in 2021. Qatar ranks first by value of labor force participation rate with a value of 88.86%, followed by Madagascar with 86.43%, from Solomon Islands with 85.22%, Iceland with 84.86%, Switzerland with 83.58%. In the middle of the table are Indonesia with a value of 68.20%, followed by Brunei Darussalam with 68.19, Costa Rica with 68.17, Congo Rep. with 68.05, Nicaragua with 67.86. The ranking is closed by Mauritania with 41.59%, Iraq with 41.52%, Yemen with 39.00%, Somalia with 34.78%, Djibouti with 32.48%.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in labor force participation rate globally between 2013 and 2021. Hungary ranks first by value of change in labor force participation rate with an amount of 17.88%, followed by Malta with 16.68%, Albania with 14.57%, Maldives with 13.33%, Bosnia and Herzegovina with 13.15%. In the middle of the table are Mexico with -0.33%, Kuwait with -0.34%, Comoros with -0.36%, Congo Dem. Rep. with -0.38%, Costa Rica with -0.38%. The ranking is closed with Rwanda with -8.19%, Guinea with -8.86%, Benin with -10.29%, Egypt with -14.26%, Venezuela with -15.72%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented below. Clusters are thus identified, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Burundi, Mozambique, Canada, Eritrea, Germany, Holland, North Korea, New Zealand, Norway, Bahamas, Vietnam, Liberia, United Kingdom, Angola, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Denmark, Sweden, United Arab Emirates, Australia, Ethiopia, Japan, Estonia, Switzerland, Peru, Austria, Latvia, Finland, Tanzania, Solomon Islands, Singapore, Madagascar, Iceland, Qatar, Lithuania, China, Thailand, Uruguay, Cambodia, Saint Lucia, Czech Republic, Nigeria, Kenya, Barbados, Portugal, the Russian Federation, Spain, Kuwait;
- *Cluster 2:* Iraq, Algeria, Tajikistan, Comoros, Mauritania, Nepal, Syria, Iran, Jordan, Yemen, Papua New Guinea, Egypt, Moldova, Somalia, Morocco, Djibouti, Sudan, Turkmenistan, Senegal, Gabon, Libya, Lebanon, Tunisia, India;
- *Cluster 3:* Congo, South Korea, Panama, Belgium, Malaysia, Brazil, Ukraine, Indonesia, Jamaica, Poland, Greece, Brunei Darussalam, Nicaragua, Vanuatu, East Timor, Haiti, Zimbabwe, Malawi, Azerbaijan, Burkina faso, Ecuador, Costa Rica, Argentina, Lesotho, Romania, Belize, Ghana, Central African Republic, Uganda, Congo Dem Rep., Hungary, Armenia, Croatia, Bulgaria, Ivory Coast, Oman, Mauritius, Serbia, Bolivia, Cuba, Mali, Luxembourg, Israel, South Sudan, Bhutan, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Albania, Slovak Republic, United States, Trinidad and Tobago, Chile, North Macedonia, Dominican Republic,

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Honduras, France, Benin, Georgia, Italy, Ireland, Malta, Colombia , Cameroon , Cyprus, Slovenia, Montenegro, Botswana, Bahrain, Paraguay, Kyrgyz Republic, Mexico.

- *Cluster 4*: Sri Lanka, Samoa, Equatorial Guinea, Togo, Sao Tome and Principe, Guinea Bissau, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, Zambia, Tonga, Bangladesh, Guyana, Sierra Leone, Uzbekistan, Fiji, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Suriname, Turkey, Chad, Guinea, South Africa, Rwanda, Gambia, Namibia, Guatemala, Cape Verde, Philippines, Laos, Maldives, El Salvador, Pakistan, Venezuela, Mongolia, Eswatini.

From the point of view of the median, the following ordering of the clusters is evident: $C1=78.75 > C3=68.68 > C4=59.04 > C2=45.72$.

Machine learning and predictions. Machine learning algorithms are proposed below for predicting the future value of the labor participation rate. Eight different algorithms are compared based on their ability to maximize the R-squared and minimize statistical errors, i.e., MAE, MSE, RMSE. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the data while the remaining 20% was used for the actual prediction. The following ordering of the algorithms is therefore identified, i.e.:

- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 4;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 11;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value equal to 14;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 17;
- Simple Regression with a payoff value of 18;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 22;
- Gradient Boosted Trees with a payoff value of 27;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 31.

Therefore, through the application of the best predictor algorithm or the Polynomial Regression it is possible to identify countries that are considered "*winner*s", or countries for which a growth in the value of the participation rate in the labor force is predicted, and the countries "*loser*s", i.e. countries for which a reduction in the value of the labor force participation rate is predicted.

Winning countries. The winning countries are indicated below: Egypt with 60.15%, Guinea with 24.47%, Mauritania with 18.72%, India with 15.53%, Cabo Verde with 15.48%, Algeria with 15.24%, Bhutan with 12.49%, Malawi with 12.39%, Vietnam with 10.46%, El Salvador with 8.56%, Guatemala with 8.42%, Tanzania with 8.15%, Cuba with 5.88%, Mozambique with 5.51%, Eritrea with 5.24%, Timor Leste with 4.34%, Lesotho with 4.16%, Iceland with 4.06%, Congo Rep 3.62%, St Vincent and the Grenadines with 3.58%, South Sudan with 3.32%, Spain with 3.09%, Israel with 3.06%, Papua New Guinea with 2.91%, Turkmenistan with 2.18%, Togo with 1.83 %, Zimbabwe with 1.57%, Bahrain with 1.37%, Mexico with 1.33%, Ukraine with 1.27%, Eswatini with 1.05%, North Macedonia with 0.46%, Ivory Coast with 0.33%.

Losing countries. The countries for which a reduction in the value of the labor force participation rate is expected are: Qatar with -0.92%, Argentina with -1.61%, Norway with -1.79%, Nicaragua with -2.41 %, Italy with -2.53%, Paraguay with -4.69%, Finland with -6.25%, Luxembourg with -7.02%, Czech Republic with -7.36%, Singapore with -7.83% , Armenia with -7.95%, Slovenia with -11.43%, Nepal with -12.01%, Croatia with -12.08%, Lebanon with -12.36%, Jamaica with -14.63%, Cambodia with -14.74%, Azerbaijan with -15.02%, Moldova with -17.25%.

Conclusions. The value of the labor force participation rate grew between 2013 and 2021 on average worldwide. Furthermore, the prediction with Polynomial Regression algorithm is predicted to further grow by a value of 0.60%. It must be considered that the value of the participation rate in the labor

market is not representative of a positive condition for the economy of the nations. In fact, the countries of cluster 1, i.e., the countries that have a high level of participation rate in the labor market, are very heterogeneous in terms of per capita income. In fact, in this cluster we find both central and northern European countries, i.e., countries with high per capita income, and African and Asian countries, i.e. countries with low per capita income. Furthermore, it must be considered that in the future it is probable that the labor participation rate could also decrease in GDP growth as well due to the application of artificial intelligence algorithms.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

	R^2	MAE	MSE	RMSE	SUM
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>PNN</i>	3	3	2	3	11
<i>Linear Regression</i>	2	2	8	2	14
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	6	4	3	4	17
<i>Simple Regression</i>	4	5	4	5	18

<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	5	6	5	6	22
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees Regression</i>	7	7	6	7	27
<i>ANN</i>	8	8	7	8	31

	2021	Prediction	Var Per
Algeria	0,197424	0,227520	15,24
Argentina	0,642352	0,632039	-1,61
Armenia	0,722304	0,664879	-7,95
Azerbaijan	0,710312	0,603648	-15,02
Bahrain	0,719891	0,729753	1,37
Bhutan	0,556563	0,626077	12,49
Cabo Verde	0,472300	0,545409	15,48
Cambodia	0,825424	0,703774	-14,74
Congo, Rep.	0,630963	0,653776	3,62
Cote d'Ivoire	0,597417	0,599387	0,33
Croatia	0,637491	0,560492	-12,08
Cuba	0,558443	0,591275	5,88
Czechia	0,786113	0,728221	-7,36
Egypt, Arab Rep.	0,199305	0,319178	60,15
El Salvador	0,515602	0,559744	8,56
Eritrea	0,824431	0,867671	5,24
Eswatini	0,353994	0,357700	1,05
Finland	0,819499	0,768256	-6,25
Guatemala	0,483866	0,524625	8,42
Guinea	0,364035	0,453096	24,47
Iceland	0,929112	0,966862	4,06
India	0,334463	0,386408	15,53
Israel	0,682408	0,703269	3,06
Italy	0,570985	0,556567	-2,53
Jamaica	0,683188	0,583238	-14,63
Lebanon	0,325841	0,285573	-12,36
Lesotho	0,589860	0,614395	4,16
Luxembourg	0,737507	0,685737	-7,02
Malawi	0,634883	0,713530	12,39
Mauritania	0,161537	0,191784	18,72
Mexico	0,563978	0,571482	1,33
Moldova	0,282858	0,233314	-17,52
Mozambique	0,813628	0,858475	5,51
Nepal	0,169786	0,149393	-12,01
Nicaragua	0,627610	0,612470	-2,41
North Macedonia	0,577602	0,580267	0,46
Norway	0,840769	0,825748	-1,79
Papua New Guinea	0,280463	0,288638	2,91
Paraguay	0,761136	0,725473	-4,69
Qatar	1,000000	0,990804	-0,92
Singapore	0,818612	0,754500	-7,83
Slovenia	0,767132	0,679457	-11,43

South Sudan	0,689255	0,712128	3,32
Spain	0,732008	0,754593	3,09
St. Vincent and the Grenadines	0,677281	0,701549	3,58
Tanzania	0,896809	0,969890	8,15
Timor-Leste	0,600575	0,626638	4,34
Togo	0,463306	0,471768	1,83
Turkmenistan	0,298700	0,305217	2,18
Ukraine	0,609303	0,617012	1,27
Vietnam	0,806638	0,890997	10,46
Zimbabwe	0,606855	0,616358	1,57

	ANN	PNN	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	Random Forest Regression
<i>R²</i>	0,879488587	0,980473896	0,904300859	0,966437285
<i>mean absolute error</i>	0,065369355	0,026262864	0,059928160	0,035933029
<i>mean squared error</i>	0,005320985	0,001134202	0,004538171	0,002001511
<i>root mean squared error</i>	0,072945081	0,033677908	0,067365950	0,044738248
	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression	Simple Regression
<i>R²</i>	0,963003527	0,988429603	0,993207768	0,97548779
<i>mean absolute error</i>	0,029396865	0,020266770	0,014000722	0,033077042
<i>mean squared error</i>	0,001573074	0,010000000	0,00E+00	0,001766619
<i>root mean squared error</i>	0,039661992	0,026393698	0,018146489	0,042031164

Rank	Country Name	2021	Rank	Country Name	2021	Rank	Country Name	2021
1	Qatar	88,86	59	Bulgaria	72,551	117	Benin	62,856
2	Madagascar	86,433	60	Azerbaijan	72,53	118	Kyrgyz Republic	62,369
3	Solomon Islands	85,226	61	Kuwait	72,292	119	Trinidad and Tobago	62,061
4	Iceland	84,864	62	Barbados	72,182	120	Mongolia	61,932
5	Switzerland	83,588	63	United States	72,073	121	Gambia, The	61,914
6	Tanzania	83,043	64	Cameroon	71,895	122	El Salvador	61,554
7	Sweden	82,795	65	South Sudan	71,343	123	Lao PDR	61,376

8	United Arab Emirates	82,532	66	Jamaica	71,001	124	Bosnia and Herzegovina	60,999
9	Netherlands	82,274	67	Israel	70,957	125	Zambia	60,939
10	Ethiopia	82,158	68	St. Vincent and the Grenadines	70,668	126	Bangladesh	60,657
11	New Zealand	81,919	69	Central African Republic	70,281	127	Saudi Arabia	60,48
12	Korea, Dem. People's Rep.	81,387	70	Ghana	70,247	128	Uzbekistan	60,446
13	Japan	80,606	71	Uganda	70,234	129	Suriname	60,159
14	Burundi	79,914	72	Belgium	70,193	130	Guatemala	59,765
15	Norway	79,884	73	Bolivia	70,132	131	Namibia	59,754
16	Canada	79,439	74	Serbia	69,993	132	South Africa	59,537
17	Denmark	79,38	75	Colombia	69,546	133	Chad	59,352
18	Cambodia	79,019	76	Vanuatu	69,5	134	Cabo Verde	59,113
19	Eritrea	78,963	77	Malaysia	69,463	135	Fiji	59,062
20	Germany	78,924	78	Panama	69,259	136	Philippines	59,008
21	Estonia	78,876	79	Georgia	69,137	137	Togo	58,606
22	Lithuania	78,835	80	Ecuador	69,104	138	Nigeria	58,461
23	Belarus	78,826	81	Albania	69,031	139	Rwanda	57,443
24	Australia	78,818	82	Korea, Rep.	68,978	140	Samoa	56,817
25	Finland	78,685	83	Argentina	68,699	141	Sri Lanka	56,705
26	Singapore	78,635	84	Brazil	68,669	142	Turkiye	56,321
27	Mozambique	78,354	85	Croatia	68,425	143	Guinea-Bissau	56,203
28	Vietnam	77,96	86	Mali	68,37	144	Sao Tome and Principe	55,983
29	Malta	77,794	87	Malawi	68,278	145	Equatorial Guinea	55,961
30	Austria	77,788	88	Indonesia	68,207	146	Venezuela, RB	55,826
31	Kazakhstan	77,675	89	Brunei Darussalam	68,196	147	Tonga	55,506
32	United Kingdom	77,439	90	Costa Rica	68,176	148	Pakistan	55,014
33	Liberia	77,172	91	Congo, Rep.	68,057	149	Sierra Leone	54,201
34	Bahamas, The	77,123	92	Nicaragua	67,868	150	Guyana	53,32
35	Angola	76,937	93	Oman	67,621	151	Guinea	53,01
36	Czechia	76,803	94	Dominican Republic	67,203	152	Eswatini	52,444
37	Latvia	76,568	95	Ukraine	66,836	153	Senegal	52,105
38	Hungary	76,148	96	Montenegro	66,764	154	India	51,343
39	China	75,816	97	Belize	66,717	155	Lebanon	50,857
40	Slovenia	75,733	98	Mauritius	66,706	156	Tunisia	50,369
41	Thailand	75,481	99	Zimbabwe	66,698	157	Libya	50,174
42	Paraguay	75,395	100	Burkina Faso	66,638	158	Sudan	49,704

43	Peru	75,316	101	Haiti	66,623	159	Turkmenistan	49,327
44	Russian Federation	75,238	102	Greece	66,515	160	Gabon	48,715
45	Portugal	75,211	103	Timor-Leste	66,344	161	Morocco	48,678
46	Slovak Republic	75,093	104	Botswana	66,279	162	Moldova	48,434
47	Uruguay	75,046	105	Congo, Dem. Rep.	66,219	163	Papua New Guinea	48,299
48	Cyprus	74,972	106	Cote d'Ivoire	66,166	164	Syrian Arab Republic	46,107
49	St. Lucia	74,716	107	Lesotho	65,74	165	Iran, Islamic Rep.	45,334
50	Ireland	74,546	108	Romania	65,221	166	Comoros	45,103
51	Kenya	74,201	109	Maldives	65,188	167	Egypt, Arab Rep.	43,724
52	Luxembourg	74,063	110	North Macedonia	65,049	168	Algeria	43,618
53	Niger	73,862	111	Italy	64,676	169	Tajikistan	42,46
54	France	73,84	112	Chile	64,344	170	Nepal	42,06
55	Spain	73,753	113	Mexico	64,281	171	Jordan	41,725
56	Armenia	73,206	114	Cuba	63,969	172	Mauritania	41,595
57	Bahrain	73,07	115	Bhutan	63,863	173	Iraq	41,521
58	Poland	72,85	116	Honduras	63,586	174	Yemen, Rep.	39,001
						175	Somalia	34,788
						176	Djibouti	32,489